

AI-based Public Policy Making: a new holistic, integrated and “AI by design” approach

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Abstract—Public policy development is becoming more and more challenging for public administrations and the recent events (first of all the Covid-19 Outbreak) demonstrated how an evidence-based approach is crucial for managing critical situations with short responses, fast adaptation, and citizens’ support. The ultimate vision of data-driven policy making entails the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a means of increasing the efficiency of the policy development and management process (i.e. going beyond development to adaptation and optimization) and boosting a more responsive, adaptive, intelligent, and citizen-centric governance. The cross-industry standard process for data mining, known as CRISP-DM, is the most widely-used open standard process model that describes common approaches used by AI experts. The paper presents how the H2020 project AI4PublicPolicy leverages this model to promote a new holistic, integrated, and “AI by design” approach for public policy making, providing the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) and the blueprints for organizational transformation. Moreover, the paper presents a practical use and validation of this approach in a real-life public policy making case.

Keywords—artificial intelligence; public policy, policy making, citizen-centric, holistic, ai by design, trustworthiness, explainability, cyber-security, interoperability

I. INTRODUCTION

Public authorities are gradually realizing a shift towards data-driven decision-making, leveraging the large amounts of data that they are collecting as part of their digital transformation. In the policy making domain, the development and validation of policies require the processing of significant volumes of diverse datasets stemming from a variety of channels and sources such as databases, open data sources, IoT infrastructures, as well as citizen-generated content, including local actors (i.e. citizens and businesses) feedback.

In this context, Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can provide a significant boost to the development and management of effective, evidence-based policies for public administrations and other policy making stakeholders, by automating the policy extraction and creation process (i.e. utilizing the respective AI tools for analyzing the datasets),

facilitating the reception and analysis of citizens’/businesses’ feedback.

Although AI tools and citizen engagement are the main pillars of this new approach, the use of explainability and cyber security techniques to trust data and AI models is of fundamental importance to enhance the transparency and accountability of the policy making process and have credible and acceptable policies.

A. Public Policy making

Public policy is an institutionalized proposal or a decided set of elements like laws, regulations, guidelines, and actions to solve or address relevant and real-world problems, guided by a conception and often implemented by programs [1].

Policymaking is typically carried out through a set of activities described as "policy-cycle" with five “generally accepted” steps:

- **Agenda setting:** This first stage involves identifying a problem that requires intervention, and proposing it as an issue to the public
- **Policy formulation:** the policy formulation stage is the setting of objectives based on a problem defined in agenda-setting, and consideration of alternative actions to achieve those objectives
- **Decision making:** this stage normally is not an exclusively rational exploration of alternatives. Rather, it is a bargaining process by those with interests in the problem with the decision-making levels of government to advance those interests, also considering budget and capability constraints.
- **Implementation:** In this stage, the decisions are translated into concrete activities
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** In this stage implementation data are analyzed to assess whether the policy is being implemented as planned, and is achieving the expected objectives

B. CRISP-DM Methodology

In 2000, as response to common issues and needs, an industry-driven methodology called Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) was introduced as an alternative to Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), a previous data mining methodology [2]. It also consolidated the original KDD model and its various extensions. The iterative executions of CRISP-DM stand as the most distinguishing feature compared to initial KDD which assumes a sequential execution of its steps. CRISP-DM, much like KDD, aims at providing practitioners with guidelines to perform data mining on large datasets.

Currently CRISP-DM is the most widely-used open standard process model that describes common approaches used by AI experts in data mining problems.

C. AI4PublicPolicy project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent, and citizen-centric development of public policies. The project aims to improve the evidence-based approach in policy making overcoming the most critical barriers and provide the means for:

- Facilitate the harvesting and correlation of relevant data
- Provide a data-driven, AI-based, and evidence-based approach to policymaking
- Promote and facilitate the collaboration between Policy Makers and AI Experts
- Involve citizens and other stakeholders in the Policy evaluation and optimization
- Boost the acceptance of the policies by presenting and explaining the Policy development outcomes
- Reuse and share Policy development models and datasets

II. AI-BASED PUBLIC POLICY MAKING

Nowadays the use of AI in public administration is often limited to specific areas (health, security, traffic management) [3] and objectives (task automation, object recognition, OCR, predictive maintenance) and it is based on mature tools.

In European Union many approaches and frameworks have been developed to support policy makers in their decision process: ePolicy [4], HART [5], PROCEDO [6], MOSAIC [7]. Even though all these projects manage and process federated data for supporting and implementing data-driven policy making, they lack the integration between various and different AI techniques and tools.

Recently, a wider adoption of AI in policy making was evaluated and experimented. State-of-the-art works and research mostly focus on:

- the use of specific AI tools or techniques like chatbots [8][9], machine learning [10], or deep learning [11] to optimize public services
- the user experience with government service provided by an AI-based technology [12],
- the AI impacts on the public policy cycle [13],

- the risks and challenges related to AI adoption, particularly on security, skills, ethics, and interpretation [14]

The AI4PublicPolicy approach described in this paper goes beyond the previous works, considering all these topics in a holistic and integrated way and proposing a completely new public policy cycle, which brings a re-engineering of the current process to make it AI-based by design, scalable, and reusable in different contexts.

Furthermore, the proposed reference model embraces the principles of open innovation and social innovation, following a participative approach where all stakeholders contribute to the design and implementation of public policies needed to address complex societal problems.

The project considered public policy as a data mining problem and adopted the CRISP-DM process as a reference for AI-based Policy Making. The new AI-based Policy Making cycle proposed by AI4PublicPolicy is depicted in Figure 1, mapped on the CRISP-DM process [2].

Figure 1. AI-based Policy Making Process

The main steps of the process are as follows:

- **Policy Definition:** In this step, the Policy Maker starts creating an Analytical Policy Model describing the Policy problem(s), associating and describing relevant Datasets for the Policy, and providing “raw” data for the defined datasets.
- **Policy Interpretation:** In this step, an AI Expert, or the Policy Maker him/herself with AutoML support, use exploratory data analysis (EDA) tools to visually explore data sets, look for similarities, patterns, and outliers, and to identify the relationships between different variables
- **Policy Extraction:** In this step, an AI Expert, or the Policy Maker him/herself with AutoML support, creates one or more AI Workflows to prepare the data and train and test AI Models based on different AI Algorithms, to provide respond (insight, recommendations) to the Policy problem(s). The Policy Maker executes the AI Models on new data, analyses the responses, and validates the AI Models.
- **Policy Evaluation:** In this step, the Policy Maker uses the simulation and explainability dashboards to better understand and explain the rationale behind the AI Models responses. Once completed this step the Policy Maker involves the relevant stakeholders (citizens, business, and other local actors) in the

Policy Evaluation creating one or more surveys on the Policy problems, AI model responses, and Policy alternatives. The Policy Maker then evaluates stakeholders' feedback, presented with a statistical or sentiment scoring, and decides to complete the Policy with actionable outcomes or optimize it taking into account stakeholders' feedback.

- **Policy Presentation and Sharing:** In this step the Policy Maker presents the final Analytical Policy Model, which represents the result of the AI-based Policy Making Process, to the relevant stakeholders and publish it in a shared catalog.

III. VPME

The AI4PublicPolicy project designed an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME), that provides fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It supports the entire AI-based policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the definition, interpretation, extraction, evaluation, and presentation of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops.

The core novelty of the VPME, with respect to the analytical platforms currently used for decision making and policy making, lies in the fact that it is specifically designed for policy development and make the policy maker able to manage the end-to-end policy making process, from policy definition to policy presentation and implementation.

A. Pillars

Figure 2 illustrates the main technical/technologies pillars of the VPME:

- AI tools like Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), and Natural Language Processing (NLP) for Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining
- Tools for citizens engagement like surveys, social media, and chatbots, supporting co-creation and virtual simulation of the policy
- Tools and techniques for transparent and trustworthy policy development like eXplainable AI (XAI) and cybersecurity for AI
- Semantic and cross-country interoperability technologies (e.g., ontologies, archetypes, ontology engineering tools) enable the sharing and repurposing of policies across different organizations and policy development contexts

Figure 2. VPME Pillars

B. Architecture

Figure 3 below presents the logical view of the VPME cloud-based platform, including the main components and the interactions between them.

Figure 3. VPME Architecture

Specifically, the components of the platform include:

- **Dataset and Policy Management:** Provides software tools to collect datasets, define policies and manage them.
- **Semantic Interoperability:** Provides the interoperability functionalities that enable the mapping between the different data formats available, in-line with an agreed set of formats.
- **Cross Country Interoperability:** Translates data from one language to another target language to boost the sharing of data and policies.
- **Datasets and Policies Catalogue:** This component is a directory of policies and datasets, which facilitates the dynamic discovery of data and policies towards facilitating reuse.
- **XAI Techniques:** This module is responsible for providing technologies and techniques for eXplainable AI.
- **Policy Explainability and Interpretation:** This component is used to produce the analysis and interpretation of the policy datasets and to provide the explainability of the AI models to help humans to understand the rationale behind policy decisions.
- **AI Security:** Incorporates AI-related cyber-defense strategies to protect AI systems against attacks (notably data poisoning and evasion attacks).
- **AutoML:** This component facilitates the selection of the optimal algorithms for a specific AI process chain. To this end, it maintains a set of well-established algorithms, which are used to drive the selection of the optimal ones.
- **Text and Sentiment Analysis:** This component provides information about the sentiment of citizens, notably sentiment related to policy decisions. From an implementation perspective, it is based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) and text analytics algorithms.
- **Policy Extraction:** Enables the AI Expert to experiment with different algorithms and create the

AI pipelines to train and validate the AI models. Moreover, it enables the Policy Maker to test the AI Models provided by the AI Experts on new data and compare them to choose the best one.

- **Policy Evaluation and Optimization** allow the simulation and evaluation of policies by making use of the opinions and feedback of local actors to propose new insights and improvements.
- **Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME):** is the main interface of the platform that integrates all the different components based on proper APIs.

The following paragraphs explain in more detail the core component of the VPME platform and of the AI-based policy making process and how AI Security and XAI techniques could add the needed trustworthiness and transparency to the process.

C. Policy Extraction component

As depicted in the Figure 4 below, it supports the Policy development process, starting from the available datasets and the defined analytical policy model, and providing AI Models and dashboards for the Policy as outcomes.

Figure 4. Policy Extraction

It provides different views for AI Experts and Policy Makers and integrates the most used opensource technologies for developing, testing, tracking, and evaluating AI solutions.

Key Policy Indicators (KPIs) are the most important elements of the analytical policy model created during the Policy Definition step. They identify the outcomes that need to be predicted, estimated, or recommended through the AI models to support the policy maker in the decision making.

Using the component’s tools, the AI Expert can create an AI project for each KPI and prepare the data, extract features, train the selected algorithm, and run multiple experiments to optimize the model. Once the experimentation phase is ended the AI expert registers the model with the best performance and prepares a testing (inference) pipeline for the Policy Maker.

During the process the two actors also interact with the “Policy Explainability and Interpretation” component” to have an interpretation of the data and the AI Models results. This component provides the tools for the Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) to identify patterns and insights that help the AI Expert during the features engineering phase. Moreover, it uses eXplainable AI (XAI) techniques to provide the Policy

Maker insights on why and how an AI model suggests a particular policy decision.

The Policy Maker can test and compare the AI models registered by the AI Experts and then, once the best model is selected, the interpretation and explainability dashboards are used to better understand how it works, visualize the outcomes and simulate policy alternatives.

D. AI Security

In recent years, as deep learning became more prevalent, the vast majority of papers published discussed attacks and defenses in the context of neural networks. Naturally, these works focused on input domains in which deep learning excels, such as the image and audio domains, where data representation is generally homogeneous and input spaces are continuous. Significant effort was dedicated to computer vision applications and related tasks, e.g., image segmentation [15], face detection [16], and more specifically, image classification [17-18]. Other domains addressed include audio [19] and malware detection; represented by binary vectors [20,21] and the classification of sparsely encoded text [22].

Figure 5. AI Security image Module

The *AI Security module* must include 3 types of data: images, text, and tabular data. Recent work on adversarial learning has mainly focused on neural networks, such as computer vision and text processing. Typically, the data in the first two domains is homogeneous, whereas domains with heterogeneous tabular datasets remain underexplored, despite their prevalence. When searching for adversarial patterns within heterogeneous input spaces, an attacker must simultaneously preserve the complex domain-specific validity rules of the data and the adversarial nature of the identified samples. As such, applying adversarial manipulations to heterogeneous datasets has proven challenging, and a generic attack method has not yet been proposed. For these reasons, for now, we have not considered a module for the defense against attacks involving tabular data. In the first phase, we were interested in the images.

The vulnerability of deep neural networks to adversarial perturbations has been widely perceived in the computer vision community: they are vulnerable to adversarial examples that are generated by adding slight but maliciously crafted perturbations to benign images.

We design a detector that is constructed by an autoencoder. This autoencoder is trained only on benign

examples. If an input is drawn from the benign dataset, the autoencoder produces a small reconstruction error. Otherwise, if an input is a significantly perturbed adversarial example, the autoencoder produces a larger reconstruction error. Starting from a work previously done [23], the idea was to create a detector independent of the dimensions of the image: otherwise, we would have had to build a specific network for each different image, in the input phase, in the construction of the inner layers and the output. Choosing instead of a different representation of the image itself, it was possible to build a potentially universal model to be able to distinguish malicious images. The autoencoder generates new features during image reconstruction: these new features are used as input for a Machine Learning model (SVM, Decision Tree, Gradient Boosting) to be used as a binary classifier to distinguish correct images from malicious ones.

For a first verification of the goodness of the idea and of the approach followed, random choices were used from various datasets (flowers, landscapes, monuments, cars, and various objects). To obtain doped images we used a specific PyTorch package (torchattacks): this package foresees the use of an Image recognition model to be used as the base of the attacks. The two models chosen were: ResNet50 (it is a model widely used as a benchmark in the context of adversarial attacks) and a recently built model such as ViT.

This AI module, connected to VPME, helps identify malicious images both in the inference and training phase. All the activities that have been described above are part of a forthcoming work: the various experiments and metrics obtained for the moment cannot be shown for this specific reason. Regarding adversarial examples in NLP, we are starting to look at some previous work [24-25]. For the moment, the activities are still in the initial stages of experimentation

E. XAI Techniques

The XAI4PublicPolicy framework [26], implemented in the context of the AI4PublicPolicy project, provides a visual environment for creating XAI dashboards for AI models. This framework requires no code for creating the XAI dashboards and targets both non-experts and experimented data scientists. The XAI4PublicPolicy framework is based on several well-known ML and XAI frameworks: Dalex, Arena, and ktrain. It supports currently tabular data and images and different ML libraries. More concretely the ones supported by Dalex (H2O, scikit-learn, Tidymodels) and Keras/TensorFlow.

The policy maker can select the AI models created through the Policy Extraction, the test datasets, and the charts of interest for explaining the decisions made by machine learning methods applied to public policies.

The explainability dashboards can be saved and linked to the Policy to be later presented to the stakeholders.

IV. ORGANIZATIONAL TRANSFORMATION

AI4PublicPolicy complements public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process of reengineering and organization transformation activities, towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

These activities include:

- revision of the policy development processes following the AI-based conceptual model and integrating the VPME;
- upskilling an reskilling of personnel;
- training on the VPME;

V. VALIDATION IN REAL-LIFE USE CASE

According to the National Road Safety Plan, coherent with the "Safe System" proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, Genoa Municipality is focused on reducing the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030. Special attention is paid to risk categories and vulnerable targets such as children and adolescents, young drivers, over-65s, cyclists, pedestrians. and users of powered two-wheelers.

A. New Policy Making Process

Figure 6 shows the new Policy Making process in the context of reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects, based on the AI4PublicPolicy VPME.

Figure 6. New Policy Making Process

Starting from the Data sources defined and the Citizens' reports and suggestions that are collected through the integration with the SegnalaCi application, the analytical policy model is defined in the VPME by the Policy Makers of the Mobility Department through the Policy management component (1).

Then a team of authorized AI experts evaluates the problem described in the policy model and work on it through the Policy Extraction component (2), generating the AI models to predict or optimize the Key Policy Indicators and the dashboards to interact with the AI models for evaluating and simulating the Policy (3).

Citizens and other stakeholders are involved in the evaluation phase through surveys (4) and their feedback (5) will be taken into account to determine the impact of the different policy alternatives (6).

Finally, the evidence-based policy recommendations are presented by the Mobility Department Policy Makers to the City Council (7). Once approved (8) they will be applied to and officially communicated to the citizens.

B. Upskilling of personnel and VPME training

Two policy makers of the Mobility department were trained on basic concepts of Artificial Intelligence (AI model, features, differences between supervised and unsupervised models, type of machine learning algorithm and related

performance metrics, sentiment analysis) and on the use of the VPME.

C. Dataset collection

The Datasets used for this policy were provided by Genoa’s municipality and consisted in geographical data, accident data, meteorological data and crossing classification data.

The geographical datasets are GIS layers of the city of Genoa that includes streets, buildings, bus stops, schools, cycle paths and more. To these layers, it was added from OpenStreetMap a layer containing all the pedestrian crossings for the city of Genoa. The main information provided by accident data is time and place of the accident, type of vehicles involved, and number of people involved. The meteorological datasets provide information about the weather conditions for the time and area each accident took place.

For meteo and accident datasets some files containing historical data for the years 2019, 2021, and 2022 were manually uploaded, then a connector to the data source was created to collect new data. Data for the year 2020 was excluded due to Covid-19 impacts.

Crossing classification data is a dataset built by the Mobility department and reporting the already classified pedestrian crossings associated with their risk of accident represented by an integer. The crossings that have the highest risk are the ones that need to be upgraded first in order of time. The urgency index represents the ordered ranking of these risks in this specific dataset.

Using the VPME Datasets interface (and the Dataset and Policy Management component), the policy maker defined the above datasets, uploaded the related files and created the connectors.

D. Policy Definition

The theme of pedestrian crossings represents a key factor for urban safety, on which the Municipality of Genoa has already launched an enhancement program aimed at reducing the risk of accidents. This program requires support in evaluating crossings to identify a priority of intervention.

Figure 7. Policy definition

In this context a first policy was defined by one of the trained policy maker, using the VPME Policies interface (and through the Dataset and Policy Management component), specifying the objective, the related datasets and the key policy indicator to predict: the urgency index of intervention

to improve the safety of the crossing, based on the risk of accident. Figure 7 shows the policy details.

E. Policy Interpretation & Extraction

In the Policy Interpretation & Extraction phases, all the data associated with the policy were involved in the exploratory data analysis (EDA). The AI Experts were able to perform feature engineering on the collected data to obtain new features. This task was performed using the VPME Policy Extraction interface, through the analytical platform Jupyter Hub. The AI-Experts, after connecting the ranking risk to all the data present in the datasets, identified the most statistically relevant features. The characteristics taken into consideration are the following:

- the number of accidents that occurred within a radius of 50 m from the intersection;
- the speed limit of the road on which there is a pedestrian crossing;
- the relative slope of the road;
- the type of lighting present in the street;
- any shielding elements that prevent the correct view of moving cars (car parks, tree-lined avenues, etc.)
- presence of specific buildings (schools, shopping centers, etc.) which increases the population density and therefore also the crossing flow of the pedestrian passage.

After the AI-Experts trained and evaluated several versions of the model with MLFlow, a final version of the model was registered on the MLFlow model registry through the Policy Extraction Toolkit.

The Policy Maker run and compared the two models on new test data and chose the one with the best performance. As shown in Table 1 below, the two best performing models were “Linear Regression” and “SVR” and the latter has been chosen since it showed a better R2 score (Coefficient of Determination) and an overall lower RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error).

Algorithm	RMSE	MAPE	LogRMSE	R2
Linear Regression	0.176	0.015	-1.735	0.998
SVR	0.130	0.028	-2.033	0.999

Table 1. Model performance on test data

For the moment, considering the number of samples with actual ground truth, the AI-Experts decided not to use any Bootstrapping method.

Figure 8. Genoa Dashboard

Therefore, a simulation dashboard was created by the AI Expert, showing a map of the city of Genoa where all the pedestrian crossings are presented and it is possible to select one or more crossings and check whether the selected points need to be upgraded or not.

In the dashboard, shown in Figure 8, the black dots correspond to the crossings that need to be classified, while the colored ones represent the already classified ones. The color (green, yellow, red) represents the risk of accident.

The Policy Maker of Mobility department used the dashboard to classify new pedestrian crossings in a specific district and determine a complete ranking. Moreover, by changing the value of the features, automatically evaluated through the provided dataset, the Policy Maker could simulate how the urgency index of the crossing changes.

F. Policy Evaluation

Based on the suggested priority for intervention on pedestrian crossings the Policy Maker, using the Policy Evaluation interface of the VPME, creates a survey to obtain citizens' opinion on the outcome. For this use case, the Policy Maker decided to create an In App survey, then publish it through a web link and not through social channels. Figure 9 shows the created survey.

This survey was used during the last co-creation workshop with a group of citizens of the specific district to evaluate the AI model or to figure out which steps to improve in the policy making process to get a more accurate AI model.

G. Results

The first result of the validation was the mindset shift in the Mobility and Police Department. All the people involved supported the new approach and the innovations in the process. Particularly both the Deputy Mayors for Mobility and Police departments gave their positive feedback on the approach and the tool, believing it will help the city council to take more informed decisions.

The second result was on the use of the VPME. Even if it was the first release of the application, the feedback collected from the policy makers, through validation questionnaires about the usability and the effectiveness of the different functions, were positive.

As an additional result, the Policy Maker's dashboard allowed Genoa's Municipality to decrease by 30% the necessary time to identify the pedestrian crossings that need intervention.

Finally, the feedback received by the stakeholders contributed to validating the correct behavior of the model and to prove its usefulness. The survey's results showed that 76% of the citizens who took the survey were satisfied by the pedestrian crossings' ranking calculated by the model.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper presented the new approach proposed by AI4PublicPolicy project, that is

- "AI by design", because it is designed on top of the most used data mining methodology
- holistic, because it considers all the aspects related to the use of AI in public policy making
- integrated, because it provides and integrates the different AI tools that address these aspects.

Figure 9. Policy evaluation survey

Moreover the paper presented the VPME platform, focusing on its core component, the Policy Extraction toolkit, and introducing the novel explainability and cyber-security technologies, based on state-of-the-art techniques, developed in the project.

The Policy Extraction component provides different views for AI Experts and Policy Makers and integrates the most used open-source technologies for developing, testing, tracking, and evaluating AI solutions. It supports the Policy development process, starting from the available datasets and the defined analytical policy model, and providing AI Models and dashboards for the Policy as outcomes.

A first validation of the new approach in real life use cases was performed by the project pilots in different domains using the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) of the VPME. The paper presented the work done in the context of Genoa Municipality, which reengineered the policy making process and used the VPME to define, develop and evaluate a policy for determining the most critical pedestrian crossing and the priority of intervention to reduce the risk of an accident. The validation led to promising results in terms of mindset shift, stakeholders' engagement and policy outcomes.

The final version of the VPME will integrate the AI-Security and XAI components to provide the needed trustworthiness and transparency for the development process and the policy results and the interoperability tools to enable sharing of datasets, policy models and AI workflows across different organizations, countries and domains.

The work about AI-Security will be published once the research activities are completed.

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